

Health Policy

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A Brief Policy Memo on Strategies to Increase Health Insurance Coverage in the United States

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To the President's Chief of Staff. I'm writing this Health Policy memo to bring strategies for addressing persistent uninsurance rates in the US. The President should consider these solutions to address the issue as part of the policy agenda for the next year.

1. Scoping the problem:

The Affordable Care Act (ACA) was enacted over ten years ago. Since then, the legislation has revolutionized the American healthcare system, covering 20 million more people and saving thousands of lives.

Notwithstanding the good influence of the Affordable Care Act on the American people and healthcare system, the previous administration has been on a mission to repeal the legislation and undo the advances gained over the last decade. ⁽¹⁾

According to the KFF article, there were around 46.5 million uninsured in 2010 compared to 27.5 in 2021. ⁽²⁾

Most of the 27.5 million uninsured are nonelderly individuals, working families, and low-income households, with six out of ten being persons of color. Most uninsured persons dwell in the South or West, reflecting regional wealth differences and public coverage availability. Moreover, most of the uninsured have been without coverage for extended periods. ⁽²⁾

Most nonelderly people in the United States acquire health insurance via their jobs. Still, not all employees are provided employer-sponsored coverage or can pay their portion of the costs if offered.

Cost is a significant barrier to healthcare for the uninsured. In addition, many legally present immigrants must wait five years after attaining qualifying immigration status before they may be eligible for Medicaid.

Because the ACA provides financial assistance to many remaining uninsured, not everyone is eligible for free or subsidized coverage.

2. Alternatives

The current system has had a good impact:

- It reduced the number of uninsured by millions.
- It protects patients with prior conditions from discrimination.
- Medicaid expansion has provided health care to millions of low-income people.
- Health care has become more affordable.
- Young people and children have greater access to coverage.
- Increased access to prescription drugs.
- Rural areas gained from the present system
- Lowered Medicare expenses for seniors
- Better protections for disabled individuals

a. Healthcare rights

Healthcare is a fundamental human right. To achieve universal health coverage for all Americans, considerable changes in healthcare funding are required. The greatest, most efficient, egalitarian health system is a public, single-payer (SP) system. The significant rise in national healthcare spending may be handled by implementing a system that generates net savings above expected trends by eliminating profit and waste. With universal coverage, clinicians may concentrate on maximizing service triage rather than working within a system governed by payers with incentives to keep costs low regardless of benefit. By partnerships with provider groups, consumers function as their insurers with SP systems, making tax money work for everyone. The consumer's decision is based on the best care to fulfill their requirements with no out-of-pocket expenses. SP is the greatest alternative for ensuring equity and justice and matching priorities with medical requirements. This strategy enhances public health since everyone will have universal access to essential care, with treatment regimens tailored to the patient's specific needs. ⁽³⁾

b. Medical Consumerism

Cost is a significant barrier to healthcare for the uninsured. Encouragement of medical consumerism would reduce the number of uninsured people. The evolution of how people engage with the healthcare system can benefit the whole sector. Engaged customers generate improved quality at reduced prices across sectors. Consumption in healthcare motivates providers to provide greater quality treatment at a cheaper cost to meet customer needs. This pressure benefits patients, healthcare providers, and healthcare payers, increasing the number of people with health insurance. ⁽⁴⁾

c. Social capital

One of the causes of many uninsured people is poverty. Social capital may assist low-income people in acquiring access to economic mobility and employment self-sufficiency. Yet, social capital

generation is dependent on creating social networks. The number of connections, the intensity of the link, and the kind of who is connected are all important considerations.

Social capital has been presented as a leverage point for comprehending the literature's collective conclusions on individual socio-economic status and income inequality. With several research confirming the relevance of social attachment for health, social capital provides an intriguing tool to learn about how social factors impact health ⁽⁵⁾

A wealth of research supports the association between various measures of social capital and health, as well as some evidence that social capital mediates the relationship between economic inequity and health. Each step down the socio-economic ladder in high-income nations is linked with lower health outcomes. This 'social gradient' argues that socio-economic health disparities may represent material disadvantage connected to socio-economic status and a psychological route associated with social position. ⁽⁶⁾

d. Provider availability and professionalism

A multifaceted strategy should include the following main pillars:

- Technology solutions to provider shortage, practitioner burnout, and improving patient care. This involves expanding telemedicine and robots.
- Recruitment solutions that address concerns such as micro-credentialing and international recruiting. This includes :
 - *Increasing graduate medical education (GME) spots.
 - *Allow internationally-trained doctors to work alongside US doctors.
 - *Offer debt forgiveness in exchange for practicing in underserved communities.
 - *Start initiatives to encourage students from underserved communities to seek medical careers. ⁽⁷⁾

3. Addressing the two foci of the chief of staff

Addressing disparities in healthcare is essential not only from social justice and equity standpoint but also for improving the nation's overall health and economic prosperity. Unfortunately, black people and other

disadvantaged groups face higher rates of disease and death across a wide range of health conditions, limiting the nation's overall health.

Health disparities are caused by underlying social and economic inequality rooted in racism. Therefore, fixing inequities is critical for social justice and enhancing our country's general health and economic development.

Four policies are required to handle provider supply.

- Restructure the present graduate medical education system by linking financing directly to medical residents rather than hospitals, as it is now. This reform will enhance training and provide governments greater leeway in deploying newly minted citizens where they are most needed.
- Reform state licensure laws and accrediting standards to remove barriers to practice.
- Offer alternatives to traditional third-party payment by enabling and encouraging direct primary-care coverage agreements and establishing stand-alone health accounts, which are legally distinct from health insurance.
- Minimize administrative and regulatory costs in medical practice, notably in Medicare programs.

Although politicians cannot fix all of the factors contributing to the impending physician shortage, these four adjustments would drastically enhance the practice environment and boost the supply of physicians. ⁽⁸⁾

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